

SJIF Impact Factor: 5.186

ISSN: 2181-0664
DOI: 10.26739/2181-0664
www.tadqiqot.uz

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Volume 3, Issue 2

2022

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

3 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 3, НОМЕР 2

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 2

Бош мухаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Мадазимов Мадамин Муминович
Ректор Андижанского Государственного
медицинского института, д.м.н., профессор
кафедры факультетской и госпитальной
хирургии

Тахририят раиси:
Председатель редакционной коллегии:
Chairman of the editorial Board:

Алексеев Андрей Анатольевич
Директор ожогового центра НМИЦ хирургии
им. В.Вишневого, главный комбустиолог
Министерства здравоохранения России, д.м.н.,
профессор.

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Салахиддинов Камалиддин Зухриддинович
доцент, д.м.н. кафедры факультетской и
госпитальной хирургии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Бош мухаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Хегай Любовь Николаевна
доцент, к.м.н., начальник отдела по координации
деятельности грантов Межвузовской научно-
исследовательской лаборатории Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Досина Маргарита Олеговна
в.н.с. ГНУ "Институт физиологии Национальной
академии наук Беларуси", к.б.н., председатель
Совета молодых ученых Отделения медицинских
наук НАН Беларуси

Маъсул котиб:
Ответственный секретарь:
Executive Secretary:

Ниязова Зебинисо Анваровна
PhD кафедры офтальмологии, детской
офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ ТАХРИРИЙ МАСЛАХАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

Хужамбердиев Мамазоир Ахмедович
д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной терапии Андижанского
Государственного медицинского института

Привалова Ирина Леонидовна
д.б.н., профессор кафедры нормальной физиологии Курского государственного медицинского университета,
заведующая лабораторией физиологии висцеральных систем НИИ физиологии (Курск)

Гаврилова Елена Анатольевна
д.м.н., профессор, заведующая кафедрой лечебной физкультуры и спортивной медицины Северо-западного
государственного медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Чурганов Олег Анатольевич
д.п.н., профессор кафедры ЛФК и спортивной медицины Северо-Западного государственного
медицинского университета им. И.И. Мечникова (Санкт-Петербург)

Салахиддинов Зухриддин Салахиддинович
д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедры ВОП №1, Андижанского государственного медицинского института

Рябчиков Денис Анатольевич
д.м.н., в.н.с. онкологического отделения хирургических методов лечения ФГБУ "НМИЦ
онкологии им. Н.Н. Блохина" Минздрава России

Гулямов Суръат Саидвалиевич
д.м.н., профессор кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, стоматологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Тереза Магалхайз

профессор, заведующая кафедрой Судебной медицины государственного университета Порту (Португалия)

Юлдашев Илхом Рузиевич

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой Аллергологии, иммунологии, микробиологии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Хамраев Абдурашид Журакулович

д.м.н., профессор кафедры госпитальной детской хирургии, Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Эрматов Низом Жумакулович

д.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой гигиены детей и подростков и гигиены питания Ташкентской медицинской академии

Рузиев Шерзод Ибодуллаевич

д.м.н., доцент кафедры судебной медицины и медицинского права Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бабич Светлана Михайловна

доцент, заведующая кафедрой социальной гигиены Андиганского государственного медицинского института

Сабирова Рихси Абдукадировна

д.м.н., профессор кафедры медицинской и биологической химии Ташкентской медицинской академии

Цеомашко Наталья Евгеньевна

д.б.н, с.н.с., заведующая отделом медико-генетических исследований МНИЛ Ташкентской медицинской академии

Хамраева Лола Салимовна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Усманходжаева Адиба Амирсаидовна

доцент, к.м.н., заведующая кафедрой Народной медицины, реабилитологии и физической культуры Ташкентской
медицинской академии

Шарипова Фарида Камильевна

к.м.н., доцент кафедры психиатрии, наркологии и детской психиатрии, медицинской психологии, психотерапии
Ташкентского педиатрического медицинского института

Бузруков Батир Тулкунович

д.м.н., профессор, заведующий кафедрой офтальмологии, детской офтальмологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Туйчиев Галибжан Урмонжонович

к.м.н., доцент, заведующий кафедрой детской хирургии, детской анестезиологии-реаниматологии с курсом
офтальмологии и стоматологии факультета усовершенствования и переподготовки врачей АГМИ

Маматхужаева Гулнора Нажмитдиновна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Офтальмологии Андиганского Государственного медицинского института

Каримова Зиёда Кушбаевна

доцент, к.м.н. кафедры Аллергологии, клинической иммунологии, микробиологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Саидходжаева Саида Набиевна

доцент, PhD кафедры неврологии, детской неврологии и медицинской генетики Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Зуфарова Зухра Хабибуллаевна

доцент, к.ф.н. кафедры промышленной технологии лекарственных средств Ташкентского фармацевтического института

Алимова Дурдона Дильмуратовна

PhD кафедры оториноларингологии, детской оториноларингологии, детской стоматологии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института

Page Maker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хўршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Qodirova S.R., Khamrabaeva F.I. STUDY OF APPLICATION OF MAGNETOTHERAPY IN COMPLEX WITH SYNBIOTIC IN RESTORING TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INTESTINAL DYSBIOSIS.....	6
2. Nabiraeva B.A., Khabilov B.N. HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PROSTHETICS WITH LUMINEERS AND CURRENT STATUS (literature review).....	12
3. Kim V.E., Mun T.O., Jandarova M.A., Tashpulatova K.M. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF CEMENT AND SCREW FIXATION DURING PROSTHETICS ON IMPLANTS.....	16
4. Khursanov Y.E., Tuxtaev J.K., Kurbonov N.A., Akhmedov R.F. MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF DEEP BURNING PATIENTS.....	21
5. Shamsiev F.M., Musajanova R.A., Ismoilova Sh.S., Xudoynazarov X.S. CLINICAL AND LABORATORY FEATURES OF CONGENITAL PNEUMONIA IN NEWBORN BABIES.....	30
6. Egamova M.A., Zufarova Z.H., Xamroxujaeva M.A. RESEARCH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF HEMOSTATIC CAPSULES.....	40
7. Maxsutova K.K., Zufarova Z.H. STUDY OF THE ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY OF CAPSULES BASED ON PLANT RAW MATERIALS.....	45
8. Irismetov M.E., Fozilov Kh.T., Khakimov Sh.K. PREOPERATIVE CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL RESULTS OF OPERATIVE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH VARUS DEFORMING OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE KNEE JOINT WITH ARTHROSCOPIC DEBRIDEMENT AND PROXIMAL FIBULAR OSTEOTOMY COMPLEX.....	50
9. Mustafakulov I.B., Khaidarov N.B., Khursanov Y.E., Umedov Kh.A. SURGICAL TACTICS IN CASE OF ISOLATED INJURIES OF SMALL AND LARGE INTESTINE.....	57
10. Amonova Z.X. STUDY OF THE HEPATOPROTECTOR PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG TAUCIN.....	63

**Qodirova S.R.,
Khamrabaeva F.I.**

Center for Professional Development of Medical Personnel
of the Ministry of Public Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan

STUDY OF APPLICATION OF MAGNETOTHERAPY IN COMPLEX WITH SYNBIOTIC IN RESTORING TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH INTESTINAL DYSBIOSIS

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559055>

ABSTRACT

This article is aimed to study and scientifically substantiate the use of magnetotherapy in combination with synbiotics in the rehabilitation treatment of patients with intestinal dysbiosis. 90 patients with colonic dysbiosis, 63 women and 27 men, aged 18-65 years, were studied. Following the study's objectives, all patients were divided into groups comparable to the main clinical and physiological characteristics. Patients of the first group (30 patients) were treated with magnetic therapy (MT) from the "Olymp-1" apparatus. 4 pairs of inductors carried out the impact - of solenoids on the area of the projection of the large intestine organs; exposure parameters: intensity - 30% - 100%, frequency 10 Hz, magnetic induction value - 5 mT. The procedures were carried out daily, lasting 15-20 minutes. The course of treatment is 10-12 procedures. Patients of the second group (30 patients) underwent complex treatment: MT according to the above method and a synbiotic consisting of an extract of Ganoderma Lucidum - 1 capsule 2 times a day with meals for meals 21 days. In the third comparison group (30 patients), the effect of MT from the "Olymp-1" apparatus (placebo) was imitated. The course of treatment consisted of 10-12 procedures. According to the above scheme, Ganoderma Lucidum extract was included in the treatment complex. The results of the conducted studies give grounds to regard the complex treatment of MT and synbiotics, consisting of Ganoderma Lucidum extract, as pathogenetically substantiated and effective in the treatment of patients with DC, which expands the arsenal of non-drug therapy means at various stages of therapeutic and restorative measures in the studied contingent of patients.

Keywords: Colon dysbiosis, treatment courses, rehabilitation measures, magnetotherapy, Ganoderma Lucidum extract.

**Кадырова С.Р.
Хамрабаева Ф.И.**

Центр развития профессиональной
квалификации медицинских работников
Министерство здравоохранения Республики Узбекистан

**ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ МАГНИТОТЕРАПИИ В КОМПЛЕКСЕ С
СИНБИОТИКОМ В ВОССТАНОВИТЕЛЬНОМ ЛЕЧЕНИИ БОЛЬНЫХ ДИСБИОЗОМ
КИШЕЧНИКА**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью данной статьи является изучение и научное обоснование применения магнитотерапии в сочетании с синбиотиками в реабилитационном лечении пациентов с дисбактериозом кишечника. Обследованы 90 пациентов с дисбактериозом толстой кишки, 63 женщины и 27 мужчин в возрасте от 18 до 65 лет. В соответствии с задачами исследования все пациенты были разделены на группы, сопоставимые по основным клинико-физиологическим характеристикам. Пациентам первой группы (30 человек) проводилась магнитотерапия (МТ) на аппарате «Олимп-1». Воздействие осуществлялось 4 парами индукторов - соленоидов на область проекции органов толстой кишки; Параметры воздействия: интенсивность - 30% - 100%, частота 10 Гц, величина магнитной индукции - 5 мТл. Процедуры проводились ежедневно по 15-20 минут. Курс лечения - 10-12 процедур. Пациентам второй группы (30 человек) проводилось комплексное лечение: МТ по указанной выше методике, а также синбиотик в составе экстракта *Ganoderma Lucidum* - по 1 капсуле 2 раза в день во время еды в течение 21 дня. В третьей группе сравнения (30 пациентов) имитировали действие МТ от аппарата «Олимп-1» (плацебо). Курс лечения составлял 10-12 процедур. Экстракт *Ganoderma Lucidum* был включен в лечебный комплекс по указанной выше схеме. Результаты проведенных исследований дают основание рассматривать комплексное лечение МТ и синбиотиков в составе экстракта *Ganoderma Lucidum* как патогенетически обоснованное и эффективное в лечении больных ДК, что расширяет арсенал средств немедикаментозной терапии на различных этапах лечебно-восстановительных мероприятий в исследуемом контингенте пациентов.

Ключевые слова: Дисбиоз толстого кишечника, лечебные курсы, меры реабилитации, магнитотерапия, экстракт *Ganoderma Lucidum*.

Қодирова С.Р.

Хамрабаева Ф.И.

ЎзССВ Тиббиёт ходимларининг
касбий малакасини ошириш маркази

**ИЧАК ДИСБИОЗИ БИЛАН ОҒРИГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШ БОСҚИЧИДА
СИНБИОТИК БИЛАН МАГНИТОТЕРАПИЯ КОМПЛЕКСИНИНГ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШ
ТАЪСИРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақоланинг мақсади - ичак дисбактериози билан оғриган беморларни реабилитация даволашда магнит терапиясини синбиотиклар билан биргаликда қўллашни ўрганиш ва илмий асослаш. Йўғон ичак дисбиози билан оғриган 18 ёшдан 65 ёшгача бўлган 90 нафар бемор, жумладан 63 нафар аёл ва 27 нафар эркак. Тадқиқот мақсадларига мувофиқ, барча беморлар асосий клиник ва физиологик хусусиятлари бўйича таққосланадиган гуруҳларга бўлинган. Биринчи гуруҳ беморлари (30 киши) “Олимп-1” аппарати ёрдамида магнитотерапия муолажасидан ўтди. Таъсирни 4 жуфт индуктор - соленоидлар йўғон ичак органларининг проекцион майдонига ўтказди; Таъсир қилиш параметрлари: интенсивлиги - 30% - 100%, частотаси 10 Гц, магнит индукция қиймати - 5 мТ. Жараён ҳар куни 15-20 дақиқа давомида амалга оширилади. Даволаш курси-10-12 муолажа. Иккинчи гуруҳ беморлари (30 киши) комплекс даволашдан ўтдилар: юқоридаги усул бўйича МТ, шунингдек *Ganoderma Lucidum* экстрактидан ташкил топган синбиотик - кунига 1 капсуладан 2 маҳал овқат вақтида 21 кун давомида қабул қилинди. Учинчи таққослаш гуруҳида (30 та бемор), “Олимп-1” аппарати (плацебо) дан МТ таъсири тақлил қилинган. Даволаш курси 10-12 муолажадан иборат эди. *Ganoderma Lucidum* экстракти юқоридаги схема бўйича даволаш комплексига киритилган. Ўтказилган тадқиқотлар натижалари *Ganoderma Lucidum* экстракти таркибидаги МТ ва *Ganoderma Lucidum* экстрактини комплекс даволашининг патогенетик жиҳатдан асосли ва ИД билан оғриган беморларни даволашда самарали деб ҳисоблашга асос беради, бу эса

Ўрганилган беморлар контингентига дори-дармонсиз терапия воситаларининг арсеналини кенгайтиради ва реабилитация чора-тадбирларнинг самарадорлигини оширади.

Калит сўзлар: Йугон ичак дисбиозини, магнитотерапия, даволаш курси, реабилитация чора-тадбирлари, Ganoderma Lucidum экстракти.

Introduction. The main tasks of modern medicine include the development of physiotherapeutic and biocorrective technologies for disease rehabilitation, the pathological process of systems that provide adaptive reactions in the body, including immune, metabolic, antitoxic, enzymatic, cytoprotective and others.

One of the complex pathological symptoms components is the development of dysbiotic conditions, which, among other diseases, is associated with the widespread and often unjustified use of antibiotic therapy in various diseases. There is data in the scientific literature showing a 100% combination of some diseases with intestinal dysbiosis (ID) [1]. This leads to reciprocal aggravation syndrome and thus complicates the treatment of this category of patients. The experience of using Ganoderma Lucidum extract (GL) in gastroenterological practice is widespread in the literature [2]. The results of recent studies are the application of physiotherapy methods at different stages of the pathogenesis of the disease, taking into account their differential and targeted effects, increasing the body's adaptive and reserve capacity and minimizing the risk of adverse and allergic reactions. [3].

Various methods of physiotherapy are successfully used in gastroenterological practice. However, the experience of using magnetotherapy in the treatment of intestinal diseases is limited [4]. Preliminary research data show that the theoretical condition for the use of magnetic therapy (MT) in patients with intestinal dysbiosis is its beneficial effect on the state of the body's regulatory systems, increased adaptive responses, improvement of regional hemodynamics in patients with various pathologies and [2] has

The aim of the study: to study and scientifically substantiate the use of magnetotherapy in combination with Ganoderma Lucidum extract in the rehabilitation of patients with intestinal dysbiosis.

Research methods: 90 patients aged 18-65 years with colon dysbiosis, including 63 women and 27 men.

In addition to general clinical studies, laboratory diagnosis of intestinal dysbiosis was performed by R.V. Eshpteynitvak and F.L. Using the method developed by Vilypanskaya (1970), endoscopic examination of the colon using the apparatus of Olympus, histological examination of the biopsy of the colonic mucosa, assessment of the state of the immune system using tests that provide quantitative indicators of cellular and humoral immunity: T- and V- lymphocytes, G, A, M class immunoglobulins in peripheral blood (methods M. Jondal et al., 1972; I. Moretta et al., 1975; G. Mancini, 1965), assessment of psychological status using a computer version of a multifactorial questionnaire for the study of personality. Questionnaire to study the person V.P. According to the Hare method (1981), the assessment of psychosomatic status (well-being, activity, mood) using an abbreviated multifactorial questionnaire test for personal examination. The data obtained were processed using various statistical methods (modified by Fisher) by calculating the Student t-criterion using the Microsoft Excel (2007) software package on an IBM PC. When appropriate samples were available, the Student Difference Test was used. An alternative F-test was used to assess the difference in stocks (percentage change in the mark's availability). Differences between mean values were considered reliable in R.

Methods of treatment. According to their main clinical and physiological characteristics, all patients were divided into comparable groups, following the study's objectives. The first group of patients (30 patients) were treated with Olympus-1 apparatus magnetic therapy (MT). The projection area of the colon organs was affected by 4 pairs of inductors - solenoids; exposure parameters: intensity - 30% - 100%, frequency 10 Gts, magnetic induction value - 5 mT. The process takes 15-20 minutes every day. The course of treatment is 10-12 treatments. The second group of patients (30 patients) underwent complex treatment: MT by the above method and a synbiotic consisting of Ganoderma Lucidum extract - 1 capsule per day 2 times a day for 21 days at mealtime.

In the third comparison group (30 patients), the effect of MT from the Olympus-1 device (placebo) was simulated. The course of treatment consisted of 10-12 treatments. Ganoderma Lucidum extract is included in the treatment according to the above scheme.

Research results:

Assessing the dynamics of pain syndrome, the advantages of complex treatment should be noted: complete elimination of pain occurred in 83.3% ($r < 0.05$) - 1-groups. In all patients with diarrhea, diarrhea was less common in groups 2 and 3 and did not change in group 3. There were also positive changes in the state of intestinal biocenosis, which was manifested by a significant improvement in the composition of anaerobic and aerobic components. In 83% of group 1 ($r < 0.05$) bifidobacteria and lactobacilli increased to normal values. In the second group, the frequency of faeces led to normalization and a decrease in flatulence in 76.2% of cases ($x_2 = 11.9$; $r = 0.031$ and $x_2 = 8.1$; $r = 0.048$ and $x_2 = 9.5$; r for the negative amine test. = 0.042 and $x_2 = 7.3$; $r = 0.053$).

When used topically for therapeutic effects in patients with intestinal dysbiosis, great attention is paid to the results of rheovasography to improve regional blood circulation in the pathological center to a certain extent. Analysis of regional blood circulation dynamics revealed an improvement in blood circulation in the abdominal organs, mainly due to an increase in vascular circulation, restoration of vascular tone, and a decrease in angiospasm in the vessels. (Table 1).

Table 1

Dynamics of pelvic rheovasography (RVG) in patients with intestinal dysbiosis

After a course of treatment

RVG indicators	1 group (MT)	2 group (Ganoderma Lucidum extract)	3 group (MT+ Ganoderma Lucidum extract)
Ri (Om)	0,039±0,0016 0,052±0,0013*	0,041±0,0017 0,069±0,01*	0,041±0,0022 0,047±0,0023
$\alpha(c)$	0,24±0,04 0,20±0,07	0,25±0,08 0,19±0,07	0,26±0,08 0,22±0,07
$\beta(c)$	0,58±0,01 0,54±0,02	0,60±0,008 0,54±0,02*	0,61 ±0,011 0,57±0,24
T(c)	0,80±0,06 0,78±0,08	0,87±0,007 0,80±0,03*	0,88±0,06 0,84±0,08
$\alpha/T(\%)$	30,0±0,26 25,6±1,24*	28,75±0,68 23,8±1,8*	31,6±0,41 28,8±2,30
Di (%)	73,9±4,50 53,2±2,7*	72,5±1,78 52,3±1,06*	60,7±0,89 57,3±2,7

Each table cell shows the indicators in the top row before treatment and the bottom row after treatment.

* - significant changes in the indicator during treatment.

At the same time, the inclusion of Ganoderma Lucidum extract in the treatment complex helped accelerate blood flow and improve blood circulation in venous vessels. The mechanisms for implementing regional hemodynamic improvements were slightly different and more specific in Group 2. In group 3 of patients, the rheography indices did not change significantly.

Immune disorders play a central role in the pathogenesis of intestinal dysbiosis [4]. Therefore, attention was paid to the study of the mechanism of action of MT as a monotherapy method for local effects on the state of the immunocompetent system and the effect of synbiotics.

Analysis of the immune state dynamics showed the advantages of complex treatment. This was characterized by an improvement in the ratio of $T\gamma$ and $T\mu$ due to the restoration of the balance of immunoregulatory T-cell subpopulations and clear differentiation of T-lymphocytes in the thymus as a significant increase in their immunoregulatory index ($R < 0.05$). In the study of immunological

parameters of patients in groups 1 and 3, only the restoration of immunoregulatory subpopulations of T μ -lymphocytes was detected. However, the immunoregulatory index did not change significantly.

A comprehensive assessment of treatment efficacy showed the advantages of complex therapy. Thus, at the end of the course of treatment, a significant improvement was noted as follows: 10% in group 1, 40% in group 2; Improvement in 1-36.7% of patients, 43.3% - 2 and 37.3% - in Group 3. 13.3% of patients were ineffective in the 1st, 0.67% - in the 2nd and 56.6% - in the 3rd groups.

The values of the Pearson criterion in the distribution of treatment outcomes in the two main groups relative to the comparison group were $\chi^2 = 10, 2$, respectively; $r = 0.038$; $\chi^2 = 16.2$; $r = 0.014$. Long-term treatment results showed that positive results were maintained for an average of 40% in 1 month and 66.7% in group 2 for 3 months. In 23.3% of 1st patients after 6 months, A positive effect was maintained in 46.7% of group 2. Recurrence of the disease after 6 months occurred in 27.6% of patients.

1st 0.33%; 2nd 57.1% 3rd groups. After 12 months, the positive effect was maintained in 13.3% of group 1 patients and 85% of group 2 patients. An increase in the inflammatory process after 12 months was observed in 46.7% of patients in group 1, 66.7% in group 2 and 20% in group 3. The high efficacy of long-term outcome-based treatment was confirmed by reliable values of the Pearson χ^2 criterion in two main groups compared to the control group; they were continuous during 12-month follow-ups (for groups 1 and 2, $\chi^2 = 23.8$; $r = 0.026$; $\chi^2 = 28.5$; $r = 0.011$).

Conclusion. Thus, the study's results allowed us to identify several positive effects of magnetotherapy in combination with synbiotics on the impact on various links of the pathogenesis of the studied disease. The vasotropic effect plays an important role in realizing the therapeutic effect of magnetotherapy. The improvement in regional hemodynamics observed in most studies resulted in a reduction in pathogenic infection in the colon, which helped improve the intestine's functional state.

The complex treatment enhances and alters magnetotherapy's analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect, has an immunocorrective effect, promotes saccharolytic microflora's growth, restores intestinal microflora's dynamic balance, and improves the function of the intestine, has a positive effect on the psycho-emotional state. One of the important components of the therapeutic efficacy of complex treatment is a decrease in the frequency of exacerbations of the disease and prolongation of the remission period, which serves as a method of secondary prevention of diseases in the reproductive system of the developed complex.

The study results provide a basis for considering that therapeutic and restorative measures are pathogenetically justified and effective in treating patients with intestinal dysbiosis, which expands the arsenal of drug-free drugs at different stages of complex therapy consisting of MT and Ganoderma Lucidum extract.

References:

1. Razumov A.N., Gusakova E.V., Efendieva M.T., Molina L.R., Ondjyu N., Doroshev N. Vozmozhnosti sinbiotikov v korrektsii narusheniy kishhechnoy mikroflory v praktike vrachey raznykh spetsialnostey. //Sb. tr. «New diagnostic and ozdorovitelno-reabilitatsionnye tekhnologii vosstanovitelnoy meditsiny-2005» - Moscow, 2005. - p.8-69.
2. Razumov A.N., Efendieva M.T., Gusakova E.V., Molina L.R., Zemlyanskaya I.V., Ondjyu N. Sovremennyye podhody k reabilitatsii bolnykh s sindrom razdrajennogo kishhechnika s pomoshchyu funktsionalnogo nutrition. // Symposium novye diagnosticheskie i ozdorovitelno-reabilitatsionnye tekhnologii vosstanovitelnoy meditsiny. - Moscow, 005.-pp. 67-68.
3. Razumov A.N., Gusakova E.V., Efendieva M.T., Molina L.R., Ondjyu N. Novye tehnologii meditsinskoy reabilitatsii bolnykh s funktsionalnymi narusheniyami tolstoy kishki. 41-426. (in Russian)
4. Gusakova E.V., Efendieva M.T., Ondjyu N., Molina L.R., Zemlyanskaya I.V. Physiotherapy in combination with synbiotics in treating patients with irritable bowel

- syndrome.//Gastroenterology in St. Petersburg. Materials of the 8th Slavic-Baltic Forum “St. Petersburg - Gastro-2006” 2006, №1-2. - pp. 41.
5. Goenka M. K., Kochhar R., Chakrabarti A., Kumar A., Gupta O., Talwar P., Mehta S. K. Candida overgrowth after treatment of duodenal ulcer. // Journal of Clinical Gastroenterology. - 2006. - №6. - V.23. - p. 7-10.
 6. Huang Y.G., Ji J.D., Hou Q.N. A study on carcinogenesis of endogenous nitrite and nitrosamine and cancer prevention. // Mutation Research. - 1996. - № 9. - p. 7-14.
 7. Kocian J. Lactobacilli in treating dyspepsia due to dismicrobia of various causes. // Vnitřni Lekarství. - 2004. - №2. - V. 40. - p. 79-83.
 8. Levine J., Dykoski R. K., Janoff E. N. Candida-Associated diarrhea: a syndrome in search credibility. // Clinical Infectious Diseases. - 1995, - № 10 - p. 881-886.
 9. Riordan S.M., McIver C. J., Wakefield D., Bolin T. D., Duncombe V.M., Thomas M.C. Small Intestinal bacterial overgrowth in the symptomatic elderly. // American Journal of Gastroenterology. - 2010. - №1. - p. 47-51.
 10. Salminen S., Salminen E. Lactulose. Lactic acid bacteria, intestinal microecology and mucosal protection.//Scandinavian Journal of Gastroenterology. - 2007. - V.222. - p. 45-48.

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

3 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

ТОМ 3, НОМЕР 2

UZBEK MEDICAL JOURNAL

VOLUME 3, ISSUE 2

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000